

Original Research

Evidence of *Bipolaris oryzae* causing brown leaf spot disease of rice (*Oryzae sativa*) in Ghana

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Abstract

A high incidence of brown leaf spot disease was observed on rice foliage during field visits, with no management strategy employed by farmers. To confirm the aetiology for the future development of a management strategy, isolation and identification of the associated fungal pathogen was carried out morphologically and confirmed molecularly through amplification and sequencing of the ITS region. Pathogenicity test on the rice variety 'AGRA' was performed to confirm Koch's postulates. The pathogen was morphologically identified to belong to the genus *Bipolaris*. A molecular analysis based on the sequencing dataset placed the isolates in the same clade as *Bipolaris oryzae*. The current results should guide plant protectionists in developing sustainable management strategies to curtail the spread of the disease in the country.

Keywords

Bipolaris spp., *B. oryzae*, brown leaf spot, rice diseases, phylogenetics, Atwima Nwabiagya District, Ghana

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Gliva *Bipolaris oryzae* dokazano povzroča bolezen rjavih listnih madežev riža (*Oryza sativa*) v Gani

Izvleček

Na poljih je bila na listih riža opažena visoka pojavnost rjave listne pegavosti in odsotnost strategije za obvladovanje te bolezni s strani kmetov. Da bi potrdili etiologijo za prihodnji razvoj strategije obvladovanja, je bila izvedena izolacija in identifikacija povezanega glivnega patogena. Identifikacijo smo izvedli morfološko in jo potrdili z molekularnimi metodami s pomočjo PCR in sekvenciranja ITS regije. Da bi potrdili Kochove postulate, je bil izveden test patogenosti na riževi sorti 'AGRA'. Patogen je bil morfološko identificiran kot pripadajoč rodu *Bipolaris*. Molekularna analiza DNA sekvenc je izolate uvrstila v isti klad kot *Bipolaris oryzae*. Sedanji rezultati bi morali voditi varstvenike rastlin pri razvoju trajnostnih strategij upravljanja za omejitev širjenja bolezni v državi.

Ključne besede

Bipolaris spp., *B. oryzae*, rjava listna pegavost, bolezen riža, filogenetika, okrožje Atwima Nwabiagya, Gana

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is an important staple cereal providing 20% of the global dietary energy requirement (Nganga et al., 2022). Africa's insatiable demand for rice at a rate of 6% positioned it as the fast-expanding market for the produce and ranked it as the second-largest global rice importer (Fontan & Mughal, 2020). This trend is projected to continue due to the rapid growth in population, urbanisation, and growing consumer preferences. The contribution of Ghana to Africa's rice importation is substantial as according to the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (2022), the average per capita rice consumption of Ghana increased from 35 kg/annum in 2016 to about 45 kg/annum in 2020 confirming Asante et al. (2020) assertion that rice is the second most consumed cereal crop in Ghana after maize. Ghana is, however, estimated to produce just about 40% of its local demand, although it has suitable land resources to boost production, compelling the importation of the commodity into the country (Ouédraogo et al., 2021).

A major limitation of rice production is the susceptibility of commercial rice varieties to several fungal pathogens. Fungal infections in rice reduce yield quantity and quality and increase the cost of production through their management. Some studies have reported on the prevalence of fungal diseases in rice farms across Ghana. Apart from the blast disease widely reported in Ghana (Nutsugah et al., 2003; Maaldu & Abebrese, 2020),

Honger et al. (2022) reported the incidence of brown leaf spot disease (BLSD) by *Curvularia lunata* in certain parts of the country. Globally, *Bipolaris* spp. and specifically *B. oryzae* are widely documented as the major cause of the BLSD in rice (CABI, 2020; Barro et al., 2021; Kabore et al., 2025). Disease symptoms similar to the descriptions of Nutsugah et al. (2003), Maaldu & Abebrese (2020) and Honger et al. (2022) were observed in some lowland rice farms in the Atwima Nwabiagya district of the Ashanti region. The incidence of brown leaf spot disease in the area is concerning, as numerous reports (IRRI, 2012; Singh et al., 2017; Mau et al., 2020; Abrol, 2022) confirm that the disease outbreak can lead to a 45% decline in the yield of susceptible rice varieties. Apart from varietal susceptibility, some reports (Hossain et al., 2014; Adanve et al., 2023) have shown that the incidence and severity of brown leaf spot disease increase in areas with high relative humidity and precipitation, a characteristic feature of lowland rice production. The occurrence of the disease could be even more worrying because the majority of producers in the study area are smallholder farmers with less access to inputs and knowledge in rice disease management.

Although *B. oryzae* is widely documented to cause BLSD, the identity and pathogenicity of *B. oryzae* on rice have not been confirmed in Ghana, more specifically in Atwima Nwabiagya District. Our study objective was to identify and confirm the pathogenicity of *B. oryzae* on rice in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection

Leaves of the rice variety "AGRA" expressing brown leaf spot disease symptoms (Fig. 1) were collected in February 2023 from 4 rice farms in the Atwima Nwabiagya North district, Ghana. On the field, five symptomatic rice leaves were sampled in a zig-zag pattern, with each plant being 5 m apart and placed in paper bags. Sampled leaves were brought to the laboratory and kept at 4 °C until fungal isolation.

Isolation and identification of fungal cultures

Before isolation, the collected samples were thoroughly washed under running water for 15 mins to eliminate all debris, sterilised with 1% sodium hypochlorite solution, serially rinsed with sterile distilled water, and blotted dry. The sterilised-dried leaves were cut into pieces to contain both healthy and diseased portions and seeded on Oxoid potato dextrose agar (PDA) media fortified with ampicillin (250 mg/l, Meiji Seika Pharma Co., Ltd.) to prevent bacterial growth contamination. Fungal colonies successfully isolated were sub-cultured on fresh PDA plates, and pure cultures were produced by the single spore method. Emerging *Bipolaris* spp. were identified based on colony

and conidia morphological features as reported in previous studies (Marin-Felix et al. 2017; Sun et al. 2020). Conidia of each isolate were observed under an Amscope microscope mounted with an Amscope digital camera, and images were taken under 400x magnification.

Molecular identification

The genomic DNA of the isolated fungi was extracted from the fungal mycelia of 5-day-old actively growing cultures on PDA using the modified CTAB method (Soalla et al., 2023). The obtained genomic DNA was transported to the laboratory of Functional Biosciences DNA Sequencing Services, Madison, United States of America (USA), for DNA amplification by PCR, and sequencing of the amplicons following standard laboratory procedures. The ITS region was amplified using ITS1F (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS4R (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3') (Carbone & Kohn, 1999). The sequence data obtained after sequence analysis were aligned using the Bioedit software version 7.2, and the identity was confirmed by comparing it with the database in the GeneBank of the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)-nBLAST analysis. Phylogenetic relationships were inferred using the neighbour-joining method with 1000 bootstrap replicates based on the combined ITS dataset in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Rice plants showing symptoms of rice brown leaf spot disease in the field.

Slika 1. Riževa rastlina, ki kaže simptome rjave listne pegavosti riža na polju.

Pathogenicity test of selected fungal species

Koch's postulates were evaluated to confirm the pathogenicity of the isolated fungi on a susceptible rice variety, 'AGRA'. The detached leaves and whole plant assays, as described by Thomas et al. (2016) and Honger et al. (2022), were used. Detached leaves were sterilised in 75 % ethanol, rinsed with sterile distilled water, allowed to dry under a laminar flow chamber, and placed in separate 90 mm Petri dishes lined with moistened Whatmann filter paper. The leaves were inoculated with the *Bipolaris* spp. spore suspensions (106 spores/ml) as described by Park et al. (2017). For the whole plant assay, the leaves of two-week-old rice seedlings were inoculated with spore suspension (106 spores/ml). Rice tissues inoculated with autoclaved water served as control treatments in both evaluations. The inoculated seedlings were covered with transparent plastic bags to provide ambient humidity and temperature. The plastic bags were removed after 24 hours, and the plants were placed on benches under a screen house ($26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 73% humidity). The inoculated seedlings and detached leaflets were observed daily for 7 and 14 days post-inoculation under detached leaves and whole plant assays, respectively, for the appearance of brown leaf spot symptoms. Where symptoms appeared, the fungus was re-isolated from the artificially inoculated tissues to complete Koch's postulates. Triplicates of the inoculated detached leaves and rice seedlings were arranged in a completely randomised design.

Results

Isolation and morphological identification of fungal isolates

Fungal isolates resembling *Bipolaris* were successfully obtained from the diseased leaf samples. Isolates KK-A and AD-A were selected as representatives for further study. Morphologically, they exhibited irregular colony shapes which appeared greyish dark with conspicuous zonation pigmentation on the front view (Fig. 2a), while dark colourisation was observed from the back (Fig. 2b). Colony diameter was 8.4 cm at 6 days after incubation. The conidia appeared dark brown, curved in shape, broader in the middle and round at the end with multiple 5-8 septations (Fig. 2C). Conidia size ranged from 52.0-74.1 μm in length.

Molecular confirmation of selected fungal isolates

The sequence data generated for this study have been deposited in the NCBI GeneBank and assigned GeneBank accession numbers PX111114.1 and PX111115.1 for isolates KK-A and AD-A, respectively. BLASTn search confirmed that the two isolates had complete identity with *Bipolaris oryzae*. Phylogenetic analysis based on the ITS gene confirmed that both KKA and AD-A clustered in a well-supported clade with reference sequences of *B. oryzae* (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Morphology and cultural features of the fungal pathogen isolated. (A) Colony front view on PDA. (B) Colony back view on PDA. (C) *Bipolaris* spp. conidia.

Slika 2. Morfologija in kulturne značilnosti izoliranega glivičnega patogena. (A) Pogled na kolonijo od spredaj na PDA. (B) Pogled na kolonijo od zadaj na PDA. (C) Konidiji *Bipolaris* spp.

Table 1. Species, strains and accession numbers of specimens used in the phylogenetic tree construction.

Tabela 1. Vrste, sevi in številke dostopa vzorcev, uporabljenih pri sestavi filogenetskega drevesa.

Specie name	Strain number	Accession number (ITS)	Reference
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	SS	PV982076.1	Samsthitha (2025)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	Bo2	PP448182.1	Vignesh and Lokesh (2024)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	ZM347	OR690743.1	Song et al. (2023)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	BO2020_CRI_2.7	OQ875830.1	Chuchiw et al. (2023)
<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	BIPOL7	OQ861268.1	Maurya (2023)
<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	BHS 4-17	ON724162.1	Tan (2022)
<i>Bipolaris coffeana</i>	BRIP 14845	KJ415525.1	Tan et al. (2014)
<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	BHS 4-17	ON724162.1	Tan (2022)
<i>Bipolaris adikaramae</i>	HSF022	MT509431.1	Ferdinandez et al. (2022)
<i>Bipolaris gossypina</i>	UEM4658	OQ743523.1	Rodrigues et al. ()
<i>Bipolaris maydis</i>	p005	PQ500574.1	Piyush et al. (2024)
<i>Bipolaris papendorffii</i>	AH-01	KC592365.1	Li et al. (2013)
<i>Bipolaris zeicola</i>	Bz_JC10	MW929303.1	Cipollone et al. (2021)
<i>Bipolaris victoriae</i>	GA2016, TE302	KX371072.1, OW984559.1	Tian and Smith (2016), Becker (2022)
<i>Bipolaris maydis</i>	Kbm1, CBS 136.29	PP988397.1, NR_138224.1	Kundu et al. (2024); Amaradasa et al. (2014)
<i>Bipolaris saccharicola</i>	CBS 155.26	KY905674.1, NR_151854.1	Marin-Felix et al. (2017)
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	A559	KX463014.1	Li (2016)
<i>B. oryzae</i>	KK-A	PX111114.1	This study
<i>B. oryzae</i>	AD-A	PX111115.1	This study

Figure 3. Phylogram generated for *Bipolaris* from neighbour-joining analysis based on ITS alignments.Slika 3. Filogram, ustvarjen za *Bipolaris* iz analize sosedskega združevanja na podlagi poravnave ITS.

Pathogenicity of selected fungal isolates

One-week post-inoculation, both detached rice leaves and whole plants showed characteristic lesion symptoms (Fig. 4A and Fig. 4B). The lesion symptoms observed initially appeared as small spots on the leaves which later appeared elliptical, narrowly linear, and coalesced to form long lesions causing leaf blight with yellowing as it progressed (Figures 4A and 4B), while the control plants and detached leaves had no visible spots after fourteen days of inoculation. Fungal pathogen isolated from symptomatic leaves of the artificially inoculated tissues was morphologically consistent with the inoculated pathogen, confirming Koch's Postulate.

Discussions

Results of the current study have established *Bipolaris oryzae* as the causal pathogen of rice brown leaf spot disease in the study area. Species of *Bipolaris* have been identified to cause multiple diseases, such as leaf spots, leaf blight, and root rot on different hosts belonging to the Poaceae family. Multiple studies (Nayak et al. 2019; Chhabra et al. 2023; Wickramasinghe et al. 2023; Priyadarshani et al. 2023) have linked *Bipolaris* to rice brown leaf spot disease.

In Ghana, major diseases of rice like the blast and brown spot caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Curvularia* spp. respectively (Nutsugah et al., 2006; Honger et al., 2022), have been reported. Nutsugah et al. (2003) associated *B. oryzae* with BLSD in Northern Ghana based solely on visual observations, without employing additional tools such as culture, molecular and pathological techniques to diagnose and confirm the pathogen. Ackaah et al. (2023) reported on the association of *B. oryzae* on rice seeds, but their study was based on morphological features. The weakness associated with the use of morphological tools may have limited the results obtained since no molecular tools were employed in the species identification. Before then, studies conducted by Oppong et al. (2022) and Honger et al. (2022), which both involved the use of molecular tools, reported *Curvularia* species instead, and it remained doubtful as to whether or not *Bipolaris* species were actually the cause of brown leaf spot disease of rice in Ghana and specifically in the study area. The study presents a significant finding with important implications for rice production. Earlier studies (Naik et al., 2016; Barua et al., 2019; Sobanbabu et al., 2018), which involved pathogenicity of *B. oryzae*, reported that it can cause seedling wilt, death, blight, and dark lesions on the culm of rice and rice spikelet, thereby reducing yield and grain quality. It has also been found on other crops like *Typha latifolia* (Berbrer et al., 2022) and *Oryza rufipogon* (Liu et al., 2021), and its negative impact on inducing leaf

Figure 4. *B. oryzae* inoculated rice leaves showing symptoms of brown leaf spots on (A) detached rice leaves and (B) whole rice plant.

Slika 4. Listi riža, okuženi z *B. oryzae*, kažejo simptome rjavih listnih madežev na (A) odtrganih listih riža in (B) celotni riževi rastlini.

spot disease on yield and grain quality has been reported. The findings of the current study have confirmed the existence of *B. oryzae* in Ghana and its pathogenic ability on the AGRA rice variety grown by farmers in the study area. Further studies are, however, required to ascertain the prevalence in the country and prompt the development of disease management strategies.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, J.A, S.L-K; methodology, T.A.B, A.D.; Software, Y.D; Validation, F.K; Formal analysis, J.O, S.L-K.; Investigation, J.A, J.O.; Resources, T.A.B; Data curation, J.A, T.A.B.; Writing—original draft preparation, S.L-K, J.A., T.A.B.; Writing—review and editing, Y.D, J.A, J.O; Visualisation,

F.K.; Supervision, J.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Disclosure Statement

The authors disclose no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

All sequence data generated during this study have been deposited in the NCBI GenBank and are freely accessible to the public. The fungal isolates obtained are preserved in the culture collection of the Department of Crop and Soil Sciences Education, AAMUSTED, Ghana. These isolates, together with other data are available from the lead author upon reasonable request.

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